

**A checklist of identified legal issues
impacting safe and efficient delivery of live-
remote exercise.**

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This checklist is provided for general informational purposes only and does not constitute legal advice. It offers illustrative, non-exhaustive examples of common scenarios and should not be relied upon as a substitute for case-specific legal assessment in any particular jurisdiction.

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1 Introduction & Background

This checklist provides an overview of various legal aspects and considerations for live remote exercise (in the following: tele-rehabilitation) services, encompassing the perspectives of different stakeholders involved. It serves as a guide for providers of live remote rehabilitation services, helping them navigate the complex legal landscape and ensure compliance with relevant laws and regulations, particularly, but not limited to, a European cross-border context. The checklist (from “2 Patients/Clients” on) is based on various categories, including the interests and needs of the individual stakeholders involved when offering tele-rehabilitation. While the legal checklist can be adapted with minor modifications for other contexts within the field of telemedicine, the specific setting of the PREFERABLE-II project was crucial for the development of this document. The EU-funded project, PREFERABLE-II, stands for personalised exercise oncology aimed at improving supportive care. The trial seeks to demonstrate the (cost-) effectiveness of live remote exercise for cancer survivors.

The primary function of law is to organise and regulate the coexistence of people in a society. To this end, it creates norms and rules that determine people's behaviour and structure their interactions. This usually involves balancing interests in order to restrict the freedoms of the individual as little as possible while at the same time safeguarding the basic values and rights of a society and other individuals. In the areas of medicine, research and the digital space, a complex construct of regulation already exists (among many others). Tele-rehabilitation services occupy a special position to some extent: on the one hand, they serve the applied clinical context as follow-up treatment following an illness and treatment. If such services are provided digitally, additional data protection aspects are engaged. If this rehabilitative service is still provided in the process of research (e.g., clinical studies, such as PREFERABLE-II), additional rules relating to research (e.g., freedom of research, etc.) apply. Finally, the component of cross-border provision of this service is another relevant area in terms of regulation. Even this rough thematic categorisation of tele-rehabilitation shows that a large number of individual interests and legal interests come into contact with each other, and must be brought into an appropriate balance.

The checklist has the following structure: The chapters are organised according to the stakeholders involved in tele-rehabilitation services (e.g. patients/clients, rehabilitation professionals, providers, etc.). In addition, we added chapters on the rehabilitation programme itself, on technical conditions and one about miscellaneous information. Each chapter starts with a brief explanation of the legal context regarding this specific stakeholder, flagged by an explanation of the potential conflicting interests from a legal perspective. It further delivers some background information on the legal norms, principles and structures in this field of law. Some of the legal sub-topics may repeat within the different chapters and sub-topics if they are relevant to more than one stakeholder/more than one typical situation. In most cases, these multiple mentions base on different legal assessments depending on the stakeholder group.

The sub-topics have been created to serve as a guide for legally relevant situations and problems that may arise during the offer of tele-rehabilitation services. The aim was to provide a description and an example for each sub-topic (if relevant). In addition, there are further references to relevant legal texts,

standards and literature recommendations. When examples are used in the checklist, these usually refer to the case study presented below (see the information box “Case Study” at the end of this chapter). The selected legal aspects (and legal aspects in general) broadly involve normative issues, making it challenging to draw a clear distinction between law and ethics. Each legal norm inherently includes an ethical consideration, resulting in overlapping aspects by necessity. This becomes clear at various points in this checklist, as aspects with normative elements that are not purely legal or ethical have also been taken into account. Normative aspects often promote a legally sound assessment of a situation in the context described such as the recommendation for professional(s) acting in accordance with the applicable ethical principles. For example, while using computer-cameras of the professional and of the patient for the described version of live remote exercise, a professional might observe problems in the patient’s home via this camera that are not within the scope of rehabilitation care, which may lead to an ethical dilemma.

In addition to the diffuse identification and categorisation of normative aspects, the legal assessment of a situation will vary based on minimally shifting conditions. This not only becomes clear in the explanations under "2 Patients/Clients" regarding the capacity to consent, but an example already alluded to above can be expanded on to illustrate this point: There is a difference between a tele-rehabilitation programme during the research and development phase, and the final product. Whilst the rehabilitation programme during its development needs to meet many regulatory requirements (such as, e.g., an assessment by an Ethics Committee, and the generation and curation of significant amounts of safety data), there are entirely different, and potentially less onerous, requirements to offer the tele-rehabilitation service as a product once it has obtained marketing authorisation (notwithstanding obligations of continuous safety monitoring of the product). Both cases show the influence of minimal changes in time, progress of the product/programme or age on the individual situation and its legal assessment. They also represent a false dichotomy in that there is no clear delineation between research and clinical application in many fields (and oncology is certainly one of them). In addition, there are a range of legal and regulatory aspects that are hard, if not impossible, to capture in an abstract format. This includes, but is not limited to, context shifts such as the integration of third countries (i.e. outside of the EU), and fundamental rights and societal issues such as equitable access to technology and innovation, and regional disparities in terms of access to digital infrastructures.

Whilst the legal interests and regulations within the context of tele-rehabilitation are summarised in this checklist, the list should only serve as an introduction and overview of the subject matter. Specific legal judgments for individual cases cannot be adequately considered in the general format of a checklist, so an individual legal assessment would be required. Please refer to the further notes at the end of this chapter and the literature references at each chapter/sub-topic, but do seek individual legal advice rather than relying on the broad nature of this guidance document.

Navigating the legal aspects of this checklist requires careful consideration and often consultation with legal experts familiar with healthcare regulations, cross-border services, and international law. Additionally, staying informed about evolving regulations and best practices in telemedicine and remote healthcare is essential for providers offering cross-border rehabilitation services in Europe. This checklist is intended as a general guide and may need to be adapted based on the specific legal framework and requirements in each jurisdiction.

1.1 Case Studies

The case studies show (partly simplified) exemplary situations of an offer for a tele-rehabilitation programme in which a patient and a rehabilitation professional are involved. The case studies also discuss the programme itself as well as the role of possible further organisations of the health system such as governmental health organisations and health insurance companies (see Figure 1 and 2). Scenario 1 describes the situation when rehabilitation professional and patient are located in the same country (for this example both are located in the Netherlands, see Figure 1). Scenario 2 focuses on the cross-border offer of tele-rehabilitation when rehabilitation professional and patient are not located in the same country; instead, the rehabilitation professional is located in the Netherlands while the patient is located in Germany (see Figure 2).

1.1.1 Scenario 1 – Same Country Offer of Tele-Rehabilitation

Figure 1: Case Study/Legal Checklist – same country offer.

Scenario 1 was used as first base for the presented case study: There is a cancer patient, located in a rural region of the Netherlands. Due to various infrastructural and personal reasons, the patient chooses a digital offer of rehabilitation as follow-up treatment after diagnosis and primary treatment. This tele-rehabilitation programme is already fully developed but can be adapted to the individual needs (in particular side effects) of patients due to the customisable structure of the programme for special or particularly prominent side effects. There is a Dutch provider with various subsidiaries also located in the Netherlands, providing rehabilitation services in different forms. One subsidiary and its rehabilitation professionals (e.g., exercise specialists, physiotherapists, occupational therapists, etc.) offer tele-rehabilitation with the help of the already described tailored exercise programme for patients in the Netherlands. The server is also located in the Netherlands. Beside the already described

stakeholders, the patient and the provider/rehabilitation professional are in contact with the applicable health insurance company in the patient’s country as well as further governmental and other health organisations.

1.1.2 Scenario 2 – Cross-Border Offer of Tele-Rehabilitation

Figure 2: Case Study/Legal Checklist – cross-border offer.

Scenario 2 was used as second base for the presented case study: There is a cancer patient, located in a rural region of Germany. Due to various infrastructural and personal reasons, the patient chooses a digital offer of rehabilitation as follow-up treatment after diagnosis and primary treatment. This tele-rehabilitation programme is already fully developed but can be adapted to the individual needs (in particular side effects) of patients due to the customisable structure of the programme for special or particularly prominent side effects. There is a Dutch provider with various subsidiaries in the Netherlands, providing rehabilitation services in different forms. One subsidiary and its rehabilitation professionals offer tele-rehabilitation with the help of the already described tailored exercise programme both in the Netherlands and in a cross-border context for other patients based in other countries within the European Union (EU). The server is located in the Netherlands. Beside the already described stakeholders, the patient and the provider/rehabilitation professional are in contact with the applicable health insurance company in the patient’s country as well as further governmental and other health organisations.

2 Patients/Clients

This section deals with the legal aspects regarding the client or patient. This means both the legal framework for the patient, and the legal conditions that the provider must observe for the benefit of the patient. In addition to the legal conditions that apply to the conventional version of rehabilitation (primarily medical law, data protection law and professional regulatory), some additional requirements apply to the digital offering of this services. The first step is to analyse which existing regulation can be transferred to the digital context, which supplementary regulation exists, and which legal areas of conflict exist that may not already be specifically regulated and must therefore be measured against more general legal standards.

The following individual interests and rights exist with view on the patient/client in the field of tele-rehabilitation. First, the patient’s physical and informational self-determination are core elements of the relationship between the healthcare professionals and the patient himself. This encompasses the whole process of tele-rehabilitation, but in particular any context regarding personal data, information about both the whole process of treatment and the tele-rehabilitation process as well as the possibility to decide free about the own engagement during the whole process. Second, the patient’s right to physical integrity is a relevant element for the tele-rehabilitation context. The patient’s property protection may also play a role in this context (e.g., insurance, reimbursement, etc.).

We would like to emphasise the following aspect in advance: the capacity to consent is not always straightforward and requires special attention in all individual cases. Per definition, the capacity to consent is the ability of a person to make an informed decision regarding medical treatments and interventions. Persons are capable of giving consent if they are able to understand and process the information provided to them by medical staff in order to make an informed decision. For instance, legal assessments of consent capacity vary significantly for minors and young adults, individuals with cognitive impairments such as advanced dementia, and others. In these particular situations, it is crucial to recognize that consent capacity cannot be automatically and definitively determined at first glance but may change over the course of an illness/treatment or with increasing age (among other individual cases). This paragraph aims to raise awareness that subchapter “a. i. Information and Consent” should be read and considered with particular attention to internal processes given these complexities.

Subtopic	Explication and/or operational “advice”: How is this addressed in my/our institution, if relevant?	Further Information
<p>a. Informational Self-Determination</p> <p>The patient's informational self-determination is a core element of the relationship between healthcare professionals and the patient. Through</p>		<p>General information (and information for Saudia Arabia in particular):</p>

<p>the right to informational self-determination, everyone should be able to decide for themselves what personal data they wish to disclose and who is authorised to use it. This includes if the patient wishes for further information regarding the tele-rehabilitation programme, if the patient would like to continue the tele-rehabilitation programme (at any point of time) and many more aspects.</p>		<p>Alhabter et al. (2023), Ethical and Legal Aspects of Telerehabilitation in Saudi Arabia, doi: 10.5195/ijt.2023.6569</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">i. Information and Consent</p> <p>This aspect is relevant for both an in-person and a digital offer of rehabilitation services as part of medical services. Nevertheless, this aspect contains further details when offered as digital service as described in the following. As part of the patient’s informational self-determination, the patient should be informed about the whole process of the programme, the pros and cons of the programme for the special situation of this unique patient, any limitations (where relevant) as well as the technical conditions for taking part in the programme in the best and most successful/supporting way. This clarification includes an ongoing exchange between professional and patient, the possibility of the patient to quit or adapt the programme on his own as well as addressing any arising problems during the programme. As result of the appropriate information of the patient, the patient consents in taking part in the programme. Furthermore, there is further consent required regarding the use of digital services/programmes/applications as well as regarding the handling and storage of personal health data of the patient.</p> <p><i>Example Scenario 1 and 2: Before starting the tele-rehabilitation programme itself, the professional (NL) and the patient (both: GER and NL) meet in a digital manner to discuss the programme, the health status of the patient, pros and cons, limitations of the programme, the used technological infrastructure as well as the handling and storage of data and many more relevant aspects, resulting in consent or not for the start of the tele-rehabilitation programme.</i></p>		<p>General Information (guideline character, partly US specific): American Telemedicine Association’s Principles for Delivering Telerehabilitation Services: Richmond et al. (2017), International Journal of Telerehabilitation, doi: 10.5195/ijt.2017.6232</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">ii. Data protection</p> <p>As part of the patient’s informational self-determination, the clarification includes information about the handling, processing and storage of the personal health data of the patient. Due to the digital form of the rehabilitation service, this includes more details against the data protection regulation. For the European context,</p>		

<p>the GDPR is relevant. Some countries have additional regulation in this field of law.</p> <p>Example: <i>see above "i. Information and Consent".</i></p>		
<p>iii. Shared-Decision Making</p> <p>Shared decision-making is a form of healthcare professional-patient interaction in which both partners are actively and responsibly involved in decision-making processes to ensure communication on equal terms.</p> <p>Example: <i>As part of the first digital meeting between the professional and the patient as well as part of the later programme, both have an ongoing process of exchange regarding different options within the tele-rehabilitation programme. There is an ongoing possibility of the patient to decide on his own based on all relevant information given by the professional through the rehabilitation programme and the whole process of treatment.</i></p>		<p>Note: Shared-Decision Making as a process in professional-patient interaction is in fact not a legal requirement but a method to give effect to legal obligations of information, capacity and consent.</p>
<p>b. Patient Safety</p> <p>Patient safety is the result of all measures in medical practices, clinics and other healthcare facilities aimed at protecting patients from avoidable harm in connection with medical treatment. Patient safety is an important part of quality assurance in medicine. This aspect mainly flags the patient's right to physical integrity and could be addressed by the professional or provider with creating a safety protocol and additional devices to ensure the best possible safety at all times.</p> <p>Example Scenario 1 and 2: <i>The patient in GER (and in the NL) is on his own during the tele-rehabilitation session. There is no other person in the room. During a specific exercise, the patient does not feel well. The professional notices a higher heart rate and starts with the actions for those cases, taking into account the individual situation. The professional has a safety protocol right beside his screen for those situations.</i></p> <p>Note/Example Scenario 1 and 2: <i>As part of a safety (screenings) protocol, there should be the information for the patient(s) and the professional(s) that there is a special need for a safe space at the patient's home to perform the tele-rehabilitation sessions at home (e.g., without any obstacles that could occur to dangerous situations).</i></p>		<p>Note: The comments in the introduction regarding the difficulty of drawing a line between ethical and legal aspects can also be considered for this sub-topic. In this case, a safety protocol is particularly suited to comprehensive quality management.</p>

<p>c. Education and Empowerment</p> <p>For the patient, one aim of the programme is to learn during the programme why these exercises help to improve and support their current situation. Patients should be encouraged to inform themselves in the accompanying materials and be encouraged to carry out the programme with its repetitions.</p>		<p>Note: this is a further example for a normative but not a strict legal aspect.</p>
<p>d. Insurance</p> <p>Depending on the jurisdiction and country, patients have different levels of health insurance and private liability insurance. Health insurance can be statutory or based on a private insurance model. It is <u>sometimes</u> possible that follow-up treatment (= rehabilitation) is covered by such insurance. Whether this also includes a digital form will vary depending on the insurance company and country.</p> <p><i>Example I: The German patient is insured under the statutory health insurance scheme, which fully covers rehabilitation under certain conditions. This patient also has private supplementary health insurance, which covers additional benefits and is intended to supplement the cover provided by statutory insurance. The patient and the provider/professional need to contact the insurance companies to ensure that they cover the costs of tele-rehabilitation in this special form.</i></p> <p><i>Example II Scenario 1 and 2: During the training, the patient damages by accident some of the materials provided by the professional for the tele-rehabilitation programme. One option is that the private liability insurance covers this damage. Another option is that professional and patient have an agreement about those situations, covering the costs for the damage as part of the general costs for taking part in the tele-rehabilitation programme (in case of slight negligence).</i></p>		
<p>e. Reimbursement</p> <p>Reimbursement can be seen as a building block alongside the insurance aspect. This becomes relevant in cases where the utilisation of a rehabilitation measure is primarily insured with regard to its implementation (e.g., via the provider), but the costs are not covered by such insurance. In these cases, it is possible that other reimbursement mechanisms will apply. This will vary from country to country.</p>		<p>The following European regulations and directives must be observed in their current versions for the situation described:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REGULATION (EC) No 883/2004 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL - REGULATION (EC) No 987/2009 OF

<p>A rehabilitation measure is usually a planned treatment measure. The legal assessment therefore differs from the regulation for emergencies and spontaneous medical measures (for example in the case of tourist stays in other EU countries or similar).</p> <p>In the case of planned medical measures, it must first be clarified whether authorisation is required and which law applies in the specific individual case. This depends on various circumstances as well as European and national regulations (including the patient's health insurance).</p>		<p>THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DIRECTIVE 2011/24/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL <p>For example, in Germany, paragraph 13 (4) and (5) of the Social Security Code V (SGB V) regulates the utilisation of medical services in other EU countries as well as the basic regulations on cost reimbursement.</p>
<p>f. Additional Participants (Care/Help/Family etc.)</p> <p>Any additional personnel or persons accompanying or participating the digital services shall be recognized and approved by the patient and the provider. Furthermore, the additional person(s) shall be informed about the process as well as the option to consent in appearing during the live sessions etc. This primarily results from the requirement of the professional/provider to ensure a safe and secure offer of tele-rehabilitation and secondly addresses the individual right of informational self-determination of both the patient and the additional person(s).</p> <p><i>Example for Scenario 1 and 2: During the last tele-rehabilitation session, the patient(s) were introduced to a new fitness exercise. The correct execution of this task is challenging for the patient (GER & NL), so he decides to ask his sister to attend the next tele-rehabilitation session to support him during this special task. This results in the required process of informing the patient, the other participants of the session, and the sister about their rights and possibilities. There might be the situation that other participants are concerned about the presence of additional persons.</i></p>		<p>This aspect includes the whole procedure of information and consent, the identification of the additional person(s), information and rules for the handling of personal data of all person(s) involved as well as the requirements for disclosure.</p>

3 Rehabilitation Professionals

This section deals with legal aspects regarding the rehabilitation professionals before, during and after offering tele-rehabilitation services. For this section, the legal analysis depends on how an individual

situation is assessed, whether the rehabilitation professional is self-employed, works for a group practice or works for a larger clinic or association. Additionally, the location of the offering rehabilitation professional could also influence the legal assessment. However, the fundamental questions from a legal perspective remain the same, so that a distinction can be made within the framework of subtopics if necessary.

Subtopic	Explication and/or operational “advice”: How is this addressed in my/our institution, if relevant?	Further Information
<p>a. Compliance</p> <p>Professionals must comply with regulations governing healthcare and rehabilitation services in both the country where the provider is located and the country where the client is located (when provider and patient are located in the same country and the offer concentrates on patients located in that specific country, only the regulation for this country applies). This includes adhering to licensing requirements, professional standards, and any specific regulations related to telemedicine or remote healthcare services.</p>		
<p>b. Data Protection and Security</p> <p>Professionals should be informed about and strictly follow the advanced standards for maintaining privacy, security, and confidentiality in tele-rehabilitation services. They are required to understand and adhere to all relevant federal, state, and professional guidelines, in addition to any specific requirements set by health-organizations concerning clinical and non-clinical documentation, the collection and storage of health data, the management of health and medical records, and the access or sharing of patient data or medical records. This ensures the protection of personal health information in compliance with applicable regulation (e.g. GDPR).</p> <p><i>Example 1 for Scenario 1 and 2: To protect the privacy and security of the patient’s health information (in GER or the NL), the professional (NL) makes use of methods like authentication and/or encryption.</i></p>		

<p>Example II for Scenario 1 and 2: <i>Before starting the tele-rehabilitation programme itself, the professional (NL) obtains consent from the patient(s) regarding the recording.</i></p>		
<p>c. Licensing and Accreditation</p> <p>Professionals should be informed about the applicable laws and regulations and comply with them, as well as incorporate the guidelines and standards of nationally recognised professional associations and other credentialing, privileging, accrediting, and regulatory requirements for licensing, certification, professional liability, and ongoing professional development or training for the use of information and communication technologies for delivering provisional services and products. In addition, they should be informed about and follow “[...] licensure regulations that contain language that may restrict types of services that can be delivered by information and communication technologies” (Richmond et al. 2017).</p>		<p><u>Telemedicine: A global approach to trends and practices</u>: Rau et al. (2022), IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee telemedicine survey – Germany</p> <p>Please note, in Germany a distinction is made between physicians who are licensed within the statutory health insurance (SHI) system and private physicians. The strict technical requirements under BMV-Ä apply only to SHI licenced physicians.</p> <p>→ Even if the requirements of the BMV-Ä are only partly relevant for rehabilitation professionals (differentiation between levels of professionals (e.g., physicians or physiotherapist, etc.), this presents possible differentiations in the various national systems.</p>
<p>d. Billing</p> <p>Professionals should be aware of existing billing and coding protocols mandated by state or federal insurance programmes, commercial insurers or private health insurers.</p>		<p>For example and among others: Richmond et al. 2017, International Journal of Telerehabilitation, doi: 10.5195/ijt.2017.6232</p>
<p>e. Insurance</p> <p>In many European countries, healthcare professionals are required to have professional liability insurance to protect themselves against potential claims of malpractice or negligence. This insurance typically covers legal costs and damages awarded to the claimant in case of a lawsuit. In</p>		

<p>addition, it can be necessary to have further insurances to protect themselves and their practice.</p> <p><i>Examples of the types of insurance that rehabilitation professionals may need include (1.) professional liability insurance, (2.) public liability insurance, (3.) employers' liability insurance, (4.) business interruption insurance, and/or (5.) health insurance.</i></p>		
<p>f. Reimbursement</p> <p>Professionals and providers should familiarise themselves with the different types of reimbursement arrangements, agreements and alternative payment methods. For example, these include fee-for-service, bundled care, accountable care organisations, shared savings and other payment models that measure cost savings and cost avoidance. This information could affect what services are offered and how billing and coding is done.</p>		
<p>g. Liability and Negligence</p> <p>Providers must understand liability issues associated with offering remote rehabilitation services, including potential claims. Clear agreements outlining responsibilities and liabilities between providers and clients should be established, considering differences in legal systems across borders. As described under "2. e. Insurance", professionals are required to have professional liability insurance to protect themselves against potential claims and costs.</p> <p>Another important aspect in connection with liability concerns the question of where legal action is taken (choice/law of the forum), and this impacts both the extent of a practitioner's liability, as well as a patient's ability and scope to obtain remedies.</p> <p><i>Example (German law): "From civil law perspective, physician's liability for medical malpractice/negligence is based on the treatment contract (section 630a BGB) and/or tort law (section 823 BGB). From a criminal law perspective, a deviation from the required quality in the treatment of a patient that results in an injury may constitute a criminal offence (§§ 223, 224, 226, 229 StGB)" (Rau et al., 2022).</i></p>		<p><u>Telemedicine: A global approach to trends and practices</u>; Rau et al. (2022), IBA Healthcare and Law Sciences Law Committee telemedicine survey – Germany</p>

<p>h. Safety</p> <p>The safety of patients during tele-rehabilitation services is the responsibility of the professionals. They should implement measures, policies and procedures to identify the location of patients during virtual sessions, provide alternative communication channels (e.g. telephone or SMS) in case of technical or communication failures and develop an emergency plan to ensure patient safety in case of health complications.</p> <p>Example I for Scenario 2 (it applies for Scenario 1 too with the contact information regarding this specific patient/country): <i>During a tele-rehabilitation session, the patient (GER) slips on the floor and is no longer responsive to the professional (NL), even after several attempts. The professional (NL) has an emergency plan for such situations, which (s)he initiates step by step. One step is to dial the German emergency number. An attempt is also made to reach the patient's (GER) emergency contact persons by telephone, who have been recorded in advance by the patient (GER) for such cases and whose consent has been given in writing. The professional (NL) remains connected via camera until someone is physically on site who can initiate further assistance measures.</i></p> <p>Example II for Scenario 1 and 2: <i>Ensuring safety also involves the professional's judgement regarding when tele-rehabilitation should be offered: after a recent second cancer treatment, the patient (GER & NL) is physically weakened and therefore at risk of falling. As there are no caregivers present to assist at the time of the reinstated tele-rehabilitation, the professional (NL) delays the restart of the programme.</i></p> <p>Example III for Scenario 1 and 2: <i>To ensure that the equipment functions safely, sufficiently and properly, the professional (NL) can use additional types of technologies or peripheral devices such as measurement tools, sound meters and/or sensor meters to provide evaluations and interventions (if agreed by the patient(s)).</i></p>		<p>American Telemedicine Association's Principles for Delivering Telerehabilitation Services: Richmond et al. (2017), International Journal of Telerehabilitation, doi: 10.5195/ijt.2017.6232</p> <p>Further example from the cited guideline: "Professionals should have guidelines in case there is a change in the physical environment or the hardware, for example. This should take into account patient factors such as usability and accessibility to promote quality of services and outcomes" (p. 67).</p>
<p>i. Language and Cultural Considerations</p> <p>Professionals offering services within one country with different spoken languages as well as offering their tele-rehabilitation services across borders must consider language barriers and cultural</p>		<p>Note: this is a further example for a normative but not a strictly speaking legal aspect.</p>

<p>differences that may influence communication and the delivery of tele-rehabilitation services. Providing services in multiple languages and adapting interventions to different cultural contexts may be necessary.</p> <p><i>Example I for Scenario 1 and 2: There might be the situation to adapt the tele-rehabilitation programme to cultures in which women are not allowed to exercise in sport clothes in the presence of other persons.</i></p> <p><i>Example II mainly for Scenario 2: The professional (NL) offers its tele-rehabilitation programme in Dutch, German and English. As the patient (GER) only speaks German, that is the language chosen for communication. Even if the professional (NL) speaks a high level of German, a simple and comprehensive language is recommended, especially in relation to consensus processes for example in relation to possible costs.</i></p>		
<p>j. Emergency Situations & Continuity of Care</p> <p>Professionals should have protocols in place for handling emergencies and ensuring continuity of care for clients, particularly in a cross-border context where access to local healthcare services may be limited. The professionals should ensure that patients know how to seek emergency assistance if needed. The protocols should include procedures for coordinating with local emergency services. If medical symptoms, complications or an emergency occur during a virtual session, the session should be cancelled/stopped. The patient should be referred to an appropriate local healthcare provider or emergency service according to the established guidelines.</p>		
<p>k. Documentation, Monitoring and Evaluation</p> <p>The documentation, monitoring and evaluation of the services offered are important aspects that avoid liability. In particular, careful documentation of the tele-rehabilitation treatment, decisive prerequisites and conditions of the individual patient as well as incidents that have occurred (e.g. emergencies) can prove in case of doubt that all duties of care of the provider/professional have been complied with. Apart from the case of a legal dispute described above, proper documentation means that a change of provider/professional or other changes can be made easily without problems due to loss of information.</p>		

<p>Example for Scenario 1 and 2: <i>After each session, the professional documents abnormalities, values, news or deviations of each participating patient in the individual patient record. (In addition: Before the next session, the professional can check the information from the last session for proper preparation and whether any changes have been occurred.)</i></p>		
<p>I. Further Education and Training</p> <p>Continuing Professional Development (CPD) should also be taken into account when offering tele-rehabilitation. Initial and further training for trainers/professionals is a quality assurance measure and is relevant/provided from professional law perspective. Individuals’ efforts in ensuring that they are trained to a state-of-the-art standard at all times directly impact the assessment of culpability/liability in negligence cases, and to some extent also in terms of criminal liability.</p> <p><i>Fictional example: Professional X has to complete five hours of education/training per year to continue the possibility to offer rehabilitation services (e.g. tele-rehabilitation)</i></p>		

4 Provider/Health Organisations/Health Authority

This section deals with legal aspects and questions regarding the provider, different health organisations, the health authority and/or the health insurance company. Not all sub-topics in this section apply to all addressees mentioned above.

Subtopic	Explication and/or operational “advice”: How is this addressed in my/our institution, if relevant?	Further Information
<p>a. Compliance</p> <p>“Organisations and professionals should be aware of and comply with laws, regulations, guidelines, and standards set forth by nationally recognized professional associations and other credentialing, privileging, accrediting, and regulatory requirements for licensing, certification,</p>		<p>Further Examples for Country Guidelines: World Health Organization (2022): Consolidated Telemedicine Implementation Guide p. 16</p>

<p>professional liability, and ongoing professional development or training for use of information and communication technologies for delivering provisional services and products” (Richmond et al., 2017). In addition, they shall be aware of and comply with any law, regulations, guidelines, etc. set by bodies on European level as well as the national requirements for both the location of the trainer/organisation and the location of the patient(s). Furthermore, licensure regulations that contain language that may restrict types of services that can be delivered by information and communication technologies as well as any other limitations should be taken into account (cf. Richmond et al., 2017).</p> <p><i>Example for Scenario 2: Before starting a tele-rehabilitation programme, the head-organisation must be aware of all applicable laws, regulations and/or guidelines related to tele-rehabilitation. In addition to applicable EU law, organizations should familiarize themselves with federal and state regulations of both where the professional works (NL) and where the recipient is located (GER). Organizations should also and in particular be aware of applicable telecommunications and digital health/e-health laws in named countries.</i></p>		<p>Digital Healthcare Act</p> <p>IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee Telemedicine Survey – Germany; Example (EU law): “<i>The Directive 2011/24/EU stipulates that the law applicable to telemedicine is the provider's place of residence. Therefore, if a provider is authorised to practise telemedicine in their own country, they can also extend this service to patients in Germany.</i>”</p> <p>➔ Even if the example is given for the context of telemedicine as a whole, tele-rehabilitation is meant to be a part of telemedicine so the requirements can be transferred for the context of this checklist.</p>
<p>b. Contractual Aspects</p> <p>Beside further contracts in the event of offering tele-rehabilitation, organisations and providers “[...] shall be aware of and comply with any additional or necessary operational or contractual requirements or arrangements with the implementation of tele-rehabilitation services. Examples include contractual agreements (e.g., service level agreements, etc.) and credentialing requirements at the site where the practitioner is located and the site where the patient is located (which may vary between states or jurisdictions)” (Richmond et al., 2017)</p>		
<p>c. Professional Regulation and Training</p> <p>In order to ensure a certain level of quality and safety, organisations and providers should introduce mechanisms to guarantee the regular training and further education of trainers/rehabilitation professionals. This relates to the area of training itself, to the area of provision via communication technologies and to the area of emergencies (first aid).</p>		<p>Example in the Netherlands: IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee Telemedicine Survey – THE NETHERLANDS</p> <p>Healthcare Quality, Complaints and Disputes Act (WKKGZ)</p>

<p>Example for Scenario 1 and 2: <i>The head-organisation should provide regular training and education for the professional (NL), for example on the latest rehabilitation approaches, techniques and methods, to ensure that the quality standards of both practising countries, Germany and the Netherlands, are met.</i></p>		
<p>d. Licensing and Accreditation</p> <p>In addition to the aforementioned considerations regarding professionals, organizations must also be cognizant of all pertinent licensure portability models (e.g., Interstate Licensure Compacts, Expedited Licensure, Limited License, etc.) that may influence interstate practice through information and communication technologies. Providers may need to obtain licenses or accreditation to offer services in multiple European countries. This could involve navigating different licensing requirements and professional standards across borders, potentially requiring partnerships or collaborations with local healthcare providers (cf. Richmond et al., 2017)</p> <p>Example for Scenario 2: <i>The head-organisation must be aware of the applicable regulations in both the Netherlands and Germany. The head-organisation should ensure that the professionals (NL) comply with applicable regulations, for example, professional liability insurance that meets the standards and requirements of the legislation in the Netherlands. It should also be checked whether the liability insurance applies to a potential liability in Germany.</i></p>		<p>Licensing in Germany: IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee Telemedicine Survey – Germany , Punkt 13</p> <p>Licensing in the Netherlands: IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee Telemedicine Survey – THE NETHERLANDS, Punkt 3</p>
<p>e. Data Security</p> <p>Beside the data security aspects regarding the rehabilitation professionals, one level higher (e.g., responsibility) the organisations and/or providers shall be aware of all relevant aspects regarding data security, data handling, data storage, and any other relevant sub-aspects regarding the proper protection of the patient’s data (and further persons involved in the programme).</p> <p>Example for Scenario 2: <i>The professional (NL) offers tele-rehabilitation via a server hosted in Germany. The head-organisation should familiarise itself with and comply with the privacy regulations of both the Netherlands and Germany. If the professional (NL) communicates with a patient in Germany via other media such as telephone or video calls, data protection regulations should also be observed. As</i></p>		<p>IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee Telemedicine Survey – Germany, Punkt 14, 20 & 21</p>

<p><i>tele-rehabilitation takes place in the patient's home (GER), other people living in the patient's household who may have access to the telemedicine services should also be considered in terms of data protection.</i></p> <p><i>Example for Scenario 1: The professional (NL) offers tele-rehabilitation via a server hosted in the Netherlands. The head organisation should familiarise itself with and comply with the privacy regulations of the Netherlands and further EU standards in terms of data protection applying to the local regulation in this field of law (GDPR).</i></p>		
<p>f. Insurance and Reimbursement</p> <p>Providers must consider how remote rehabilitation services will be reimbursed and whether insurance coverage applies across borders (Scenario 2). This may involve negotiating agreements with insurers or government healthcare systems in different countries to ensure reimbursement for services provided.</p> <p><i>Example: See above, "3. patient, e. Insurance"</i></p>		<p>For the legal situation in Germany:</p> <p><i>IBA Healthcare and Life Sciences Law Committee Telemedicine Survey – Germany, Punkt 8</i></p> <p>Additional information about the statutory health insurance and private insurance options:</p> <p>Bundesamt für soziale Sicherung (2023): Digitalisierung in der gesetzlichen KV und der sozialen PV</p>
<p>g. Liability and Negligence</p> <p>Comparable to the aspects mentioned above regarding the rehabilitation professionals, organisations and/or providers shall inform and teach their practitioners about any liability causing procedure and educate their staff for responsible procedures and actions.</p> <p><i>Example for Scenario 1 and 2: The professional (NL) may inappropriately collect, store or disclose the patient's personal health information without complying with the relevant data protection guidelines. If a patient suffers harm due to this, the relevant liability regulations should be taken into account. The head-organisation is responsible for informing professionals about their legal obligations in both countries and training them accordingly so that they can avoid an event of misconduct and act responsibly.</i></p>		

<p>h. Emergency Situations & Continuity of Care</p> <p>Comparable to the aspects mentioned above regarding the rehabilitation professionals, organisations and/or providers shall be aware of emergencies. Safety (screening) protocols shall ensure a safe and an as risk-free as possible environment for the digital rehabilitation services.</p> <p><i>Example for Scenario 1 and 2: The head-organisation could use a safety screening protocol to ensure that every professional who conducts a tele-rehabilitation session with a patient is aware of an emergency procedure. During a tele-rehabilitation session, the patient might suddenly complain of medical conditions such as chest pain, shortness of breath and show signs of discomfort. Due to the physical distance, it is not possible for the professional to help directly. Nevertheless, the professional has to be prepared to take immediate action to help the patient, such as having emergency contact information ready for local emergency services or guidance on how to carry out the first aid measures set out in the safety protocol.</i></p>		
<p>i. Documentation, Monitoring and Evaluation</p> <p>The documentation, monitoring and evaluation of the services offered are important aspects that avoid liability (see “3. k. Documentation, Monitoring and Evaluation).</p> <p>This includes the following aspects: evaluation of the tele-rehabilitation programme itself regarding safety aspects to identify potential risks, evaluating the quality of the service, and continuing the viability of the programme (quality management aspects, safety aspects, etc.). Additionally, this includes the evaluation of the professionals/trainers with regard to safety aspects as well as the evaluation of the training materials (hygiene, re-use by other patients, safety aspects, etc.).</p> <p>Beside of the aspects mentioned above, documentation, monitoring and evaluation can include statistical data on acceptance and progress as well as the possibility to identify possible data for research.</p>		<p>This is a further example for a normative aspect. The documentation might be necessary from a legal point of view, but it also contains normative dimensions.</p>
<p>j. Cross-Border Dispute Resolution</p> <p>In the event of disputes between providers and clients across borders (scenario 2), mechanisms for cross-border dispute resolution must be</p>		

<p>considered. This may involve arbitration agreements or adherence to applicable international laws and regulations. In addition, the question regarding the legal venue (place of jurisdiction) shall be discussed and regulated before the start of any tele-rehabilitation programme.</p>		
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5 Telecommunication Infrastructure

This section deals with the information and communication technology that should form the basis of a tele-rehabilitation offer. It deals with the legal requirements for technical systems when it comes to a professional-patient-relationship, but also before and after the training sessions itself.

Subtopic	Explication and/or operational “advice”: How is this addressed in my/our institution, if relevant?	Further Information
<p>a. Data Security</p> <p>This aspect concerns the entire data security surrounding the tele-rehabilitation programme. Not only should the programme itself (see below) have security structures for the handling, processing and storage of data, but there should also be a concept for the handling, documentation, storage and, if necessary, destruction/non-storage of data for the offer/programme as a whole.</p> <p><i>Example: The provider chooses a programme, which is in harmony with the national and international requirements for data security. The location of the server can be a characteristic for the decision as well as the declaration regarding the handling of data (e.g., health data, personal data etc.)</i></p>		<p>See, e.g., technical norms such as ISO/IEC 27001</p>
<p>b. Technical Education</p> <p>The provider/professional shall consider offering and supplementing the teaching materials/educational sessions with technical information and support. It might be an option to implement technical support structures for the patients.</p> <p><i>Example: During a training session, the patient has problems with his/her audio connection and is</i></p>		

<p><i>unsure how to solve this problem. (S)He asks his/her questions/concerns in the chatroom, which is supervised by additional personnel on the site of the professional to answer/solve those technical questions/problems.</i></p>		
<p>c. Videoconference Tool</p> <p>The provider/professional shall choose a safe and secure videoconference tool, if this is not part of the tele-rehabilitation programme itself, that a specific tool shall be used. This contains the personal and health data security of all participants, e.g. the rehabilitation professional, the patient, further attending persons etc.</p> <p>In addition, the videoconference tool shall be checked beforehand regarding its functions and possibilities. For example, on the one hand functions like transcriptions could be helpful for the tele-rehabilitation situation but on the other hand, this includes possible risks regarding the data safety of all persons involved as well as potential updates within the tool, so the legal assessment might change over the time of use.</p>		

6 Tailored Tele-Rehabilitation Programme

This section deals with aspects regarding the tele-rehabilitation programme itself. Depending on the circumstances, the programme can either still be in development or an already designed and tested programme can be used. The legal issues in this context are particularly relevant for users such as rehabilitation professionals, and for higher-level providers (if any). In some cases, however, there may also be aspects that need to be considered by patients.

Subtopic	Explication and/or operational “advice”: How is this addressed in my/our institution, if relevant?	Further Information
<p>a. Licensing & Copyright</p> <p>Both the licensing and the copyright for the programme to be used or for the main user (e.g. professional) must be clarified. In some cases, this can lead to restrictions on use or distribution, which must be observed by both the provider and the professional. The user in form of the patient may also be subject to certain rights and obligations regarding copyright (e.g. unauthorised distribution of content, etc.).</p>		

<p>b. Authentication process</p> <p>In some cases, it may be necessary for both the professional and the patient to authenticate themselves to be able to use the programme legally. However, proof of identity should be provided for the professional-patient-relationship and the associated medical documentation of the rehabilitation programme for liability reasons.</p> <p><i>Example I for both Scenarios: Before starting the tele-rehabilitation programme, the professional and the patient meet (in a digital manner) to give all the relevant information and for the consent of the patient with the training programme (see above). During this meeting, the patient identifies him/herself with his/her ID to the professional.</i></p> <p><i>Example II for both Scenarios: During the tele-rehabilitation programme, the patient and the professional have individual log-in-data for the video conference-tool as well as for the programme (educational materials etc.).</i></p>		
<p>c. Data security</p> <p>When selecting the programme, it must be ensured that it complies with the applicable national and European data protection regulations. This applies in particular to the server and the data protection provisions of the provider of the programme (if it was not designed in-house and conformity with the applicable provisions can therefore be ensured).</p> <p><i>Example for both Scenarios: The professional and the provider (NL) are choosing a programme, which can be customised in conformity with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and with further national regulation in this field (NL and GER).</i></p>		
<p>d. Emergency protocol & Negligence</p> <p>In addition to the comments on emergencies made above, it should be considered that the programme itself might provide emergency plans or protocols for the specific design of the programme's content (in order to prevent any case of negligence). This should be checked before the interventions are carried out. If not, a plan for emergencies should still be developed by provider and professional (see above).</p>		

7 Miscellaneous

This final section of the checklist is intended to cover a wide variety of aspects and thus serve as a "catch-all" for other relevant legal aspects in the scenario of tele-rehabilitation services.

Subtopic	Explication and/or operational "advice": How is this addressed in my/our institution, if relevant?	Further Information
<p>a. Ethics Committee</p> <p>The conduct of clinical trials requires the consultation and approval of an ethics committee (for example when developing a tele-rehabilitation programme as a new product for cancer patients and testing it in clinical research). This may be required at different levels and may be associated with different regulatory requirements (national regulations, European regulations, regulations of a hospital, etc.).</p>		
<p>b. Forecasting/Horizon Screening</p> <p>With increasing technological progress and other innovations in our world, new regulatory challenges are emerging. It is the responsibility of all parties involved who want to offer tele-rehabilitation (and other medical services, etc.) to keep themselves informed about the current status of legal regulations and conditions. Even this checklist can only reflect the legal situation at a certain point in time (also in the further development of later versions).</p>	ongoing for all	